

EFFECT OF FLAX FIBERS INDIVIDUALIZATION ON TENSILE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FLAX/EPOXY UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE

G. Coroller^{1,2,*}, A. Lefevre^{1,3}, A. Le Duigou¹, A. Bourmaud¹, G. Ausias¹, C. Baley¹

¹ LIMATB, Université de Bretagne Sud, Lorient, France

² Cooper Standard France, Vitré

³ Laboratoire PBS, Université de Rouen, Rouen, France

* Corresponding author (guillaume.coroller@univ-ubs.fr)

Keywords: *flax fiber composite, tensile failure, micromechanical analysis*

1 General introduction

In a unidirectional composite, the fiber reinforcement effect is not only due to the intrinsic properties of fibers. Fibers alignment and their spatial distribution have a high impact on the mechanical properties of the composite. In the stem of the plant, flax fibers are link into bundle of 10-40 elementary fibers [1]. Fibers isolation process is divided into three steps: retting, schutching and hackling. This process can lead to various individualized fibers content which have an impact on the mechanical properties [2].

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

Three different varieties of flax fibers cultivated in France were used in this study (Hermes, Marylin and Andrea). These varieties have been chosen for their differences and the dispersion of their mechanical properties induced by various growth conditions (hail for Andrea) or years (2003 for Hermes and 2009 for Marylin and Andrea) [3]. They were dew retted on the field before being scutched. Only the Hermes fibers were hackled. E-glass fiber extracts from industrial roving will be the reference of the study. The fibers were textilo-plastic sized.

An epoxy resin (Axson, Epolam 2020) was used as matrix. It was mixed with its amine hardener at 100:34 ratios. After hardening for 24 hours at 25 °C, all samples were post-cured following supplier recommendations (3 hrs - 40 °C; 2 hrs - 60 °C; 2 hrs - 80 °C; 5 hrs - 100 °C).

2.2 Preparation of the unidirectional composite

Different content of fibers bundles of a length of 10 cm were impregnated with epoxy. They were then put into a 100mm long aluminium mould with a 6x2

mm² section opened on each side. Figure 1 shows a sketch of the system.

The small cross section of the mould induces the unidirectional resin flow during the compression and preferential orientation of the fibers in the composite. The control of fiber content is described below. Fiber glass tabs ($\pm 45^\circ$) were bonded on the end of the tensile sample with an Araldite adhesive to reduce the risk of breakage in the jaws during the tensile test.

Fig.1. Moulding the unidirectional composite

2.3 Density and fiber content measurements

The measuring of the fiber content was carried out by density measurement, with a balance Mettler Toledo. Samples are weighed both in air and in pure ethanol and witch allows the density calculation. The fiber volume fraction (V_f) and the density are linked together through a simple mixture law.

2.4 Tensile test on single fibers

Tensile tests on single fibers were carried out at a controlled temperature (23 °C) and relative humidity (48 %) to measure longitudinal mechanical properties (Young's modulus, ultimate strength and failure strain) of single flax fibers were determined. The length of the elementary fibers being in average in the range of 20-30 mm, they were stuck on a paper frame to have a gauge length of 10 mm. The fiber was clamped on a universal MTS type tensile testing machine equipped with a 2 N capacity load

cell, and loaded at a constant crosshead speed of 1 mm/min up to rupture. The determination of the mechanical properties was made in accordance with the NFT 25-704 standard which takes into account the compliance of the loading frame. For each variety of fibre, at least 90 fibers were tested. Before the tensile test, the diameter of every fiber was measured from six points taken along the fiber with an optical microscope. A statistical analysis based on the Weibull model was performed on the tensile strength results.

2.5 Characterisation of fiber / matrix adhesion through microbond testing

The droplets were placed on the flax or glass fibers using a single glass fiber which had been dipped in the epoxy resin. Curing is then conducted following resin suppliers advice.

Fig. 2. Scheme of the micro droplet debonding test [4]

Microbond specimens were then checked under optical microscope to control the droplet geometry, length and height. Samples with defects were systematically rejected. Besides being symmetrical, micro droplets need to be smaller than 150 μm length otherwise the fiber will break. At least 120 specimens were tested for each test conditions. Then the flax or the glass fiber with the epoxy micro droplet were mounted in the razor blades device and continuously observed with a microscope (Figure 2). The fiber was pulled out of the droplet while the latter was constrained by the knife edges. The loading rate during debonding was 0.1 mm/min on a tensile machine equipped with a load cell of 2N. Apparent shear strength τ_{app} was calculated by dividing the debonding force by the embedded area [5].

2.6 Tensile tests on the composites

Tensile tests on longitudinal direction were carried out on the composites with a MTS Synergie RT/1000 at a controlled temperature of 23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, a relative humidity of 48 %, and a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. The load was measured with a 10 kN sensor, and an axial extensometer with a nominal length of 25 mm (L_0) was used for the sample strain. The results come from an average of at least 10 tested samples.

2.7 Observation of the microstructure

The microstructure analysis helped to validate the results of the fiber content analysis which were obtained through density measurement, and to ensure that no visible defects, such as porosities, could be found. Samples were embedded in an epoxy resin before polishing. They were then metallized with gold before being observed through a JEOL JSM 6460LV scanning electron microscope. Images were processed using image processing software (ImageJ) to separate the fibers from the matrix. After an appropriate thresholding on the grey level, a morphological analysis tool could be applied to get the area of each fiber in the picture. For each composite, three random cross sections were used, 10 pictures were taken to cover the whole area. A morphological analysis was then carried out on 30 pictures for each composite, thereby representing a studied surface of $2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$.

2.8 Predicting the composite failure

Despite a large dispersion of mechanical properties of flax fibers, we can estimate that the elongation at break of the fibers is lower than that of the matrix ($\epsilon_{\text{flax}} \sim 2\%$ and $\epsilon_{\text{epoxy}} \sim 3.1\%$). Assuming an assembly of fibers in the form of a bundle which would be perfectly aligned and embedded in a matrix, the evaluation of the tensile strength can be written as:

$$\sigma_{\text{Composite}} = V_f \sigma_{f_L} + (1 - V_f) \sigma'_m \quad (1)$$

where σ'_m is the stress undergone by the matrix at the failure of the composite. The σ_{f_L} parameter corresponds to the maximum stress that can be borne by the fibers in the composite. This stress is lower than the maximum stress that can be applied to individual fibers. The tensile strength of a bundle of multiple fibers, in the absence of any matrix, is given by Daniels [6]. He assumes that the entire load is carried by the fibers that have not yet been broken,

and the fiber stress is written writes the fiber stress as:

$$\sigma_{f_L} = \frac{\sigma_0 m}{mLe} \frac{1}{m} \quad (2)$$

where m , et σ_0 are the parameters of the Weibull distribution (respectively shape and scale parameters), L is the bundle length and e is the exponential. In the presence of a matrix, the fibers may be subjected to loading as their length is greater than a certain critical L_C length. Rosen [7] has defined composites as series of identical layers of elements whose axial dimension are some “critical length” (L_C). He assumes that the failure of one of those elements causes the failure of the composite, and that the stress is:

$$\sigma_{f_L} = \frac{\sigma_0 m}{mL_C e} \frac{1}{m} \quad (3)$$

Based on the model given by Kelly-Tyson [8], an evaluation of the critical length can be proposed, which relies on the interfacial shear strength τ_{app} (IFSS), the average fibers stress at break $\langle\sigma\rangle$ and the radius R of the fibers. It can be written as follows:

$$L_c = R \frac{\langle\sigma\rangle}{\tau_{app}} \quad (4)$$

Finally, the stress undergone by the matrix (σ'_m) can be calculated with the Young's moduli of the matrix (E_m) and of the fiber (E_f) as follows:

$$\sigma'_m = \frac{\sigma_{f_L} E_m}{E_{f_L}} \quad (5)$$

Due to its relevance with our materials, the model given by Rosen (equation 5) was chosen to fit the composite strengths.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Tensile behavior of flax fiber

Tensile test have been performed on single fiber. The Young's modulus of flax fibers varies significantly, depending on the origin, ranging from 48.3 ± 13.8 GPa (Hermes and Andrea) to 57.1 ± 15.5 GPa (Marylin). Marylin and Hermes have an average stress at break of 1135 MPa and 1066 MPa, respectively. Variety Andrea, which has been exposed to hail, has a lower strength: 840 Mpa. According to Griffith [9] the tensile strength of a fiber is governed by the presence of a weak link which causes the breaking of the structure. This strength is also sensitive to interactions between the various components of the fiber, and ensures the load transfer to the cellulose microfibrils [10].

Tensile strength has been analyzed statistically and Fig. 4 shows the tensile strength of elementary fibers in Weibull coordinates.

Fig. 3. Modelling of Weibull of the tensile strength of elementary fibers. (●) Glass fiber, (■) Flax fiber Hermes, (▲) Flax fiber Marilyn and (◆) Flax fiber Andrea. Dotted line is the model of Weibull with a confidence interval of 95%

This helps to determinate the Weibull modulus (m) and the shape parameter (σ_0) of the distributions. Glass and flax fibers Hermes and Marilyn can be fit by a two parameters Weibull law because most of the points are between the two dotted lines representing the confidence interval. Due to its important break slope in breakage probability, flax fibers Andrea exhibit a bimodal behavior. This characterizes a second group of defects that manages the tensile strength.

Average tensile strength and Weibull parameters are given in Table 1.

Nom	σ_{max} (MPa)	m	σ_0
Hermes	1066 ± 342	3.5	1185
Andrea	841 ± 300	3.0	943
Marylin	1135 ± 495	2.5	1282
Glass	1765 ± 432	4.2	1968

Table 1. Average tensile strength and Weibull parameters of the strength distribution of single fiber

3.2 Microstructure of composites

Figure 4 shows the surface distributions of reinforcement obtain after image analysis of the composite's cross sections. It is compared to the surface distribution of single fibers. The glass fibers

Figure 4. Composites SEM images: (A) Hermes, (B) Andrea, (C) Marilyn and (D) Glass. Histogram: surface distribution reinforcement sin the composite. Red line, surface distribution of single fiber

are completely individualized in the composite, and have a relatively homogeneous distribution through the composite cross section. Hermes fibers seem to be highly individualized (Fig. 4-a) in the composite thanks to the hackling step. Compare to the Marilyn and Andrea, there is more single fibers in the Hermes composite than in the other reinforced with flax fiber. Image analysis of several a cross sections helps to determine the single fiber content in the composite. For glass 100 % of the reinforcement is well divided. Hermes variety witch was hackled, have a single content fiber of 93 %, Andrea and Marilyn show respectively a single fiber content of 74 % and 69 %. This point highlights the important role of hackling in obtaining highly individualized fibers in the composite.

3.3 Studies of unidirectional composites

3.3.1 Study of interfacial shear strength (IFSS)

We found an interfacial shear strength (IFSS) of 22.3 ± 2.1 MPa (Table 2), showing a real adherence between the fibers and the matrix. The flax/epoxy bond strength is however weaker than the glass/epoxy bond, and the IFSS for glass is consequently higher. The values that are presented are consistent with the literature [11, 12].

Material	τ_{app} (MPa)
Glass fiber/Epoxy	37.2 ± 4.6
Flax Hermes/ Epoxy	22.3 ± 2.1

Table 2. Influence of fiber nature on interfacial properties

3.3.2 Tensile properties of UD

Composites reinforced with Hermes fibers and Marilyn fibers show higher tensile strengths than

those found in the literature: with a fiber content of around 50 %, they respectively show a stress at break of 408 MPa and 364 MPa whereas, with the same fiber content, composites reinforced with Andrea fibers reach 290 MPa. Fiber alignment, absence of defect such as porosities, and homogeneous distribution of the fibers are key parameters in optimizing the composites tensile strength. The method used for the composites manufacturing implies a high control of these parameters.

Hermes and Marilyn single fibers have very closed stresses at break (Tab. 1). Composites reinforced with Hermes fibers, have a tensile strength 11 % higher.

To understand this phenomenon, the mixing rule can be modified by calculating the real matrix strength at fiber breakage, and by introducing an efficiency factor (k , cf. Eq. 9). This efficiency factor illustrates the fiber individualization state.

$$\sigma_{UD} = k \cdot V_f \cdot \sigma_{L,f} + 1 - V_f \cdot \sigma_{L,f} \cdot \frac{E_m}{E_{L,f}} \quad (9)$$

where σ_{UD} and $\sigma_{L,f}$ are respectively the tensile strength of the unidirectional composite and of the elementary fiber. We can notice that the k values are similar for Hermes and glass fibers with an average value of 0.68 and 0.66, respectively.

This result proves the importance of the fiber dispersion and individualization on the composites mechanical properties as well as on their strain at break. For the Andrea and Marilyn fibers, the k values are lower (0.56 and 0.60 respectively) showing that, despite good mechanical properties (for Marilyn) the dispersion state remains a major parameter for an optimal reinforcement.

3.3.3 Prediction of UD tensile strength

Figure 5 compares the experimental results in longitudinal tensile properties with the theoretical values obtained from the model. Rosen's model provides an upper limit of tensile failure for composites reinforced with glass fibers and composites reinforced with Hermes fibers.

Applying this model to the composites reinforced with the Marilyn fibers and Andrea fibers leads to an overestimation of the failure (Fig. 5) due to the low fiber individualization content in such composites.

Fig 5. Comparison of Rosen model (— —) and experimental data: composite reinforced with (●) Glass fiber, (■) Flax fiber Hermes, (▲) Flax fiber Marilyn and (◆) Flax fiber Andrea (▲)

3 Conclusions

We studied the influence of elementary fibers properties, their individualization and the fiber/matrix bond strength on the tensile behaviour of associated unidirectional composites. The elementary fiber characterization showed different mechanical properties and fiber strengths, as evidenced by a Weibull analysis. Morphological analyses highlighted the importance of a hackling step for fiber dispersion; this process reduces the number of bundles in the final composite. The analysis of the UD composites mechanical properties confirms this point; although the Young's modulus values are similar to the mixture rule prediction whatever the fiber dispersion, it is not the case for the tensile strength. There is a major stake in elaborating composites with great fiber individualization, especially for the materials strength.

In the last section of the paper, the composites strength was estimated thanks to the Rosen model. The use of this model evidenced a good correlation between the experimental and estimated strengths for well individualized fibers.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the CTLN (S.C.A Teillage du plateau du Neubourg) for supplying the flax fibers, the Ministry of Research and Innovating Technologies, Région Bretagne and Région Normandie for their financial support.

References

- [1] C. Baley, "Analysis of the flax fibres tensile behaviour and analysis of the tensile stiffness increase," *Compos Part A-Appl S*, vol. 33, pp. 939-948, 07/01/ 2002.
- [2] J. Andersons, R. Joffe, E. Spārniņš, and D. Weichert, "Modeling the effect of reinforcement discontinuity on the tensile strength of UD flax fiber composites," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 46, pp. 5104-5110, // 2011.
- [3] G. Coroller, A. Lefeuvre, A. L. Duigou, A. Bourmaud, G. Ausias, T. Gaudry, *et al.*, "Effect of flax fibres individualisation on tensile failure of flax/epoxy unidirectional composite," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2013.
- [4] P. Zinck, H. D. Wagner, L. Salmon, and J. F. Gerard, "Are microcomposites realistic models of the fibre/matrix interface? I. Micromechanical modelling," *Polymer*, vol. 42, pp. 5401-5413, 06// 2001.
- [5] B. Miller, P. Muri, and L. Rebenfeld, "A microbond method for determination of the shear strength of a fiber/resin interface," *Compos Sci Technol*, vol. 28, pp. 17-32, // 1987.
- [6] H. E. Daniels, "The Statistical Theory of the Strength of Bundles of Threads. I," *Proc R Soc Lon Ser-A*, vol. 183, pp. 405-435, June 18, 1945 1945.
- [7] B. W. Rosen, "Tensile Failure of Fibrous Composites," *AIAA JOURNAL*, vol. 2, pp. 1985-1991, 1964.
- [8] A. Kelly and W. R. Tyson, "Tensile properties of fibre-reinforced metals: Copper/tungsten and copper/molybdenum," *J Mech Phys Solids*, vol. 13, pp. 329-350, 12// 1965.
- [9] A. A. Griffith, "The Phenomena of Rupture and Flow in Solids," *Philos T R Soc S-A*, vol. 221, pp. 163-198, January 1, 1921 1921.
- [10] C. Baley, C. Morvan, and Y. Grohens, "Influence of the Absorbed Water on the Tensile Strength of Flax Fibers," *Macromol Sy*, vol. 222, pp. 195-202, 03/01/ 2005.
- [11] F. M. Zhao and N. Takeda, "Effect of interfacial adhesion and statistical fiber strength on tensile strength of unidirectional glass fiber/epoxy composites. Part I: experiment results," *Compos Part A-Appl S*, vol. 31, pp. 1203-1214, 2000.
- [12] A. le Duigou, A. Bourmaud, E. Balnois, P. Davies, and C. Baley, "Improving the interfacial properties between flax fibres and PLLA by a water fibre treatment and drying cycle," *Ind Crop Prod*, vol. 39, pp. 31-39, 09// 2012.